
Homes Infrastructure Based Assessment for Better Living Standards and Good Health

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ABSTRACT

The daily activities of man revolves around daily drinking of water when eating or to quench thirst and removal of unwated waste products from the system in order to stay healthy and strong. Sources, safety, quality and quantity of water and where to deposit the resultant waste product from the body becomes of importance in ones daily life and activities. This calls for the assessment of water sources, quality and usage, sanitation, electricity together with the human waste products in our homes. This is the reason for this research work. Data was collected on three major parameters; water, sanitation and electrcity and assessed towards meeting the sustainable development goal six and seven. The adaptive methodology for this research work is visit to homes, assessment and investigation of water potentials in the homes, usage, quantity, quality and sanitation towards meeting the sustainable developmental goals six and seven. Research findings indicated that inhabitants live in self – contained owned apartments, self – contained rented apartments, rented compound houses and family compound houses. Three main utilities usage established by the research are on water, sanitation and electricity. 38 respondents indicating 38% have water, sanitation and electricity in the homes to support daily lives. 51 people representing 51 percent have standing pipes in the homes to meet daily needs. 42 respondents representing 42% indicated that the waste disposal system is good whiles 47% said it is very good. This is so because they believe the waste bins provided by waste management organization at vantage points helps households to dispose their refuse very well.

Keywords: *Water, sanitation, electricity, sustainable development goals (SDG), compound house, management, households.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Water an economic good is a vital product useful to man in running our daily homes and lives. Activities in homes such as cooking, eating, washing, bathing, cleaning, decoration such as painting etc involves the use of water. Our behaviour toward water use is vital when it comes to the rate of consumption as water is a scarce good in most areas in Ghana especially in the northern region during the dry season. It therefore becomes necessary for us to use water wisely and effectively for the benefit of home, community and country. Illegal gold mining activities in Ghana has deteriorated the water bodies in Ghana and in Nsutem hence resulting to ground water abstraction through borehole drilling for the community. The sustainable development goals six looks at clean water and sanitation for all especially in developing countries like Ghana and in a community like Nsutem. Clean water implies the water produced by Ghana water Company or community water and Sanitation Agency should be of quality, healthy and get to the homes uncontaminated. Some water obtained from well-constructed boreholes are 20% deficient of quality hence the need for further treatment before usage. This has resulted in most of the people within the community resulting to buying sachet water for their homes. This leads to an increase in water consumption cost in the homes as they cannot drink the polluted water. This is a burden on the community as most

inhabitants and local farmers and traders making water consumption cost high.

The main source of water for the community is borehole by community water and sanitation and those funded by NGO's. There is no networked piped water system to serve the community. Children and women therefore makes use buckets and containers to access the water for their homes after walking few or several meters depending on proximity from the borehole. There are two water sources in the community namely river Birim and river Supong. These two river sources have be destroyed and polluted to a higher extent due to illegal gold mining activities in the community. This is the reason for resorting to boreholes as the main sources of water for the community. Once the water are obtained from the boreholes, they are stored in containers, barrels and buckets for daily activities. There is cost associated for each bucket and the resultant number of buckets once fetches for the homes. Children are the most at work when it comes to fetching of water for the homes in order to meet water demands at the homes. Children gets up at 5:00am to fill barrels and containers before preparing for school in Nsutem community within Ghana.

Sanitation issues in the home is another important target to be addressed by the sustainable development goals (SDGs) six which considers clean water and sanitation. Sanitation issues in Ghana and within the Nsutem community has deteriorated as

compared to the 1990s when there was serious enforcement of sanitation procedures and actions by the Environmental Health Service. This has led to siting of sanitation facilities at unprescribed points such as close to water sources and uncontrolled disposal of refuse and home waste. Siting boreholes close to sanitation facilities which could result in draining of human waste into aquifers generating water for abstraction upstream for storage and consumption. Most homes have installed sanitation facilities but these need to be in good standing and efficient towards the propagation of the gospel of the six sustainable development goals within the Nsutem community. Inefficient management and usage of sanitation facilities in the homes are likely to result in disease leading to home management cost burden on the family. Children are the most affected when there are problems of water quality, quantity and bad sanitation practices in the homes. Community inhabitants also make use of public toilet facilities but on a lighter note as most homes have installed toilet facilities. Correlation between flushing toilets and piped water networked system cannot be seen in about 93% homes as there are no networked piped water systems in the community. Sanitation is affected when piped water networked systems are not properly done and managed within a community. This cannot be said of the Nsutem community as there is no networked piped water system in the community. And important sanitation issue face by the community is the

improper disposal of waste or garbage making the community surroundings unhygienic always.

2 REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

2.1 Sanitation Assessment

Globally, 2.4 billion people lack improved sanitation, and 946 million people practice open defecation (WHO/UNICEF, 2015). The United Nations reaffirmed the importance of sanitation by including it in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which calls for ending open defecation and universal access to adequate and equitable sanitation (UN General Assembly, 2015). The SDGs also set out the means of implementation as strengthening the participation of local communities and capacity building support for developing countries. Community-led total sanitation (CLTS) is an approach to addressing open defecation that triggers emotions to generate a collective demand for sanitation within a community. Community-led total sanitation (CLTS) emerged in the year 2000, and has since spread to over 60 countries, many of which now include it in national policy (Institute of Development Studies, 2016). CLTS has a role to play in addressing the SDGs, as it is participatory, generally includes capacity building, and has shown promise in addressing open defecation (Kar and Chambers, 2008; Pickering et al., 2015). However, it is not always effective (Guiteras et al., 2015), and seems to be most appropriate under certain settings, such

as high baseline open defecation (Crocker et al., 2016b) and high social capital (Cameron et al., 2015; Crocker et al., 2016a) discussion of factors strain the sustainability of CLTS outcomes (Cavill et al., 2014). The review found that CLTS outcomes were reported to be more sustainable where there was a supportive enabling environment (e.g. sufficient follow-up visits were conducted), where communities had market access to latrine products and materials, and where communities were socially cohesive.

There are very few studies that report on the sustainability of any type of sanitation intervention (Garn et al., 2016), and generating evidence on longer term outcomes of sanitation interventions is a research priority (Waddington et al., 2009). Two studies report longer term latrine use following sanitation interventions: one 5 years after a latrine-provision project in Bangladesh (Hoque et al., 1996), and another 2–9 years after programs across 8 countries that included latrine promotion (Cairncross and Shordt, 2004). We conducted a study to assess how sanitation outcomes of four CLTS interventions in Ethiopia and Ghana changed one year after the interventions had finished. We previously published evaluations of the four CLTS interventions that were based on surveys conducted before and immediately after the interventions (Crocker et al., 2016a,b). The previously published evaluations focus on the effectiveness of training health workers, teachers, and natural leaders to lead or support CLTS facilitation, and include recommendations on

where and how to engage these local actors. In the initial evaluations, we found that open defecation decreased during all four interventions. In Ethiopia, teacher-facilitated CLTS was initially less effective than health extension worker-facilitated CLTS. In Ghana, training natural leaders increased the impact of CLTS. Thus, our second objective in this study was to assess if the conclusions from the original evaluations are still sound given new longer-term survey data. Our third objective was to assess other predictors of sustained latrine use.

2.2 Wash intervention

WASH services provide for water availability and quality, presence of sanitation facilities, and availability of soap and water for hand washing (WHO/UNICEF REPORT, 2015). A joint WHO/UNICEF report shows that globally, provision of WASH services in health care facilities is low, and the current levels of service are far less than the required 100% coverage by 2030. The report also notes that large disparities in WASH services in health care facilities exist between and within countries (WHO, 2015). Provision of water is lowest in the African Region, with 42% of all health care facilities lacking an improved source on-site or nearby. However, provision of sanitation services was much better with only 16% of all health care facilities in the African Region lacking access to improved sanitation ((WHO, 2015). It has also been reported that large variations have been observed at subnational level, by settings and by type of health care facility within the same country, with smaller facilities in

rural areas having disproportionately fewer WASH services compared to larger facilities (e.g., hospitals) in urban areas ((WHO, 2015). Almost half the people in the developing world have one or more of the main diseases or infections associated with inadequate water supply and sanitation (Bertram et. al., 2005). Inadequate drinking water, sanitation, and hygiene in non-household settings, such as schools, health care facilities, and workplaces, impact the health, education, welfare, and productivity of populations, particularly in low- and middle income countries (Cronk et. al., 2015; Cronk et. al., 2018). Health-care-associated infections affect hundreds of millions of patients every year, with 15% of patients estimated to develop one or more infections during a hospital stay (Allegranzi et. al., 2015). Unsafe water and sanitation and poor hygiene practices in health care facilities lead to health-care-acquired infections (Guo et. al., 2017).

3 STUDY AREA DESCRIPTION

This research work is embarked in Nsutem community in the Eastern Region of Ghana which has a population of about 7000 (2021 population census). The Nsutem community makes use of water in variable amounts but the most important affected in times water crises are children and women. Most of the women are shop operators in front of houses or in containers involved in the selling of goods and services. This helps in making profit to better owners' lives, children and family. One main good being sold by these shops is bagged water for

drinking in homes as they cannot make use of borehole water because of its quality. Depicted in **Fig. 1** is the map of the study area. Indigenous within the community are also involved in activities such as coconut business, farming, gold mining other businesses which is making the community lively and enriching the lives of indigenous and migrants. Within the community too, water vendors can be seen at lorry stations selling in bowls on heads to travelers and divers at the station. These sachet water are produced by pure water companies outside the community and are brought to the community in trucks for selling and buying by the shop owners and water operating shops.

Fig 1: Map of the Fanteakwa South depicting the study area

3. Methodology used to obtain research results

Every research has a method employed by the researcher in order to obtain desired results for dissemination. The method employed for this research is the Questionnaire, Assessment and Observation Based Method (QAOBM). In this process, researcher reviews works done on water and sanitation, prepares questionnaires, visits homes and distributes them for answering by the indigenous within the community. In the same vain, researcher observes and assesses water and

sanitation status in the individual homes within the community. Sorting for views and opinions from respondents goes beyond the prepared questionnaires towards gaining in-depth knowledge about what community members are doing in order to meet the sustainable development goal six for their good health and wellbeing.

4 RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Household assessment and importance

Nsutem as a community in the Eastern Region in Ghana is a gold mining community serving as habitat for hundreds of people. It's a normal community with different housing system serving as abode for people to sleep and do all kinds of things before going about their daily works. During the research, 100 respondents were interviewed to sort for their opinions and understanding on health and sanitation towards meeting the sustainable development goal six. 64% were females and 36% were male as depicted in Fig. 1 below.

Table 1: Type of Housing used

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Self - Contained owned apartment	18	18.0	18.0	18.0
	Self - Contained rented apartment	20	20.0	20.0	38.0
	Rented Compound House	52	52.0	52.0	90.0
	Family Compound House	10	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Fig. 2: Type of Gender

The housing system of the research area is assessed to know and analyze the different housing system supporting daily lives. After assessment, 18 respondents representing 18% live in self – contained owned apartment which are decent houses with well tidy environments to live in. 20 respondents representing 20% live in self – contained rented apartments which are also sited around decent areas within the community. 52 respondents representing 52% live in rented compound houses within the community as seen in **Table 1**. The research established that, such areas are not within decent tidy areas within the community as refuse and untidy surroundings can be seen in such areas. People living in such areas throw refuses around and does burn their waste materials in gardens and at the back of their houses. This makes the surroundings unhealthy and dangerous to live as microorganisms are abundant due to the unhealthy nature of the surroundings as depicted in **Fig. 3**. 10 people representing 10% live in family compound houses. The family compound house system has issues with healthy household and environment as cleaning the house and surroundings is a challenge among inhabitants within the house. Sweeping and cleaning of house and surroundings is always shared among inhabitants as they sweep the house in turns throughout the week. This is supposed to be done by each inhabitants within the home but not so as some residents feel reluctant to do it. This leaves the houses dirty and surroundings unclean. This is a challenged faced by landlords and in keeping the homes clean and healthy

to promote sustainable Development Goal (SDG) six. In Ghana and at Nsutem, the rented compound house system and family compound house system usually is not a peaceful and serene environment to live in as sweeping of the house and keeping the surrounding clean is a problem and leads to fight among inhabitants.

Fig 3: Types of housing system used at Nsutem

4.2 Home utility assessment

To make life and living standards meaningful and enjoyable, there is the need for utility satisfaction within the homes and

within the community. During the research, various utilities were assessed and this includes water system, sanitation system and electricity system to assess their availability, usage and impacts in the homes. During the interview and answering of questionnaires, 4 people representing 4% indicated that, they have only water system in their house. They do not have electricity and sanitation system in their homes. If they have to visit the toilets, they go to a nearby house to ease themselves as there is no public toilet facility within that area. 9 respondents representing only 9% have only toilet facility in the house with no water system and electricity. 38 respondents indicating 38% have water, sanitation and electricity in the homes to support daily lives as depicted in Table 2.

Table 2: Utility system in the Homes

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Water System	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
Sanitation System	9	9.0	9.0	13.0
Electricity System	14	14.0	14.0	27.0
Water, Sanitation and Electricity System	38	38.0	38.0	65.0
Water and Sanitation system	2	2.0	2.0	67.0

Water and Electricity System	4	4.0	4.0	71.0
Sanitation and Electricity System	29	29.0	29.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Since they have the three utility system in the homes, it helps keep the house and environment clean as water system help in embarking on daily activities such as washing, cooking, bathing, cleaning etc. The sanitation system helps them to ease themselves easily without going to a nearby house or easing themselves in the bushes or gardens as can be seen in **Fig 4**. 2 respondents of the sample people indicated that they have only water and sanitation system within their homes to support daily lives in meeting the sustainable development goal six.

Fig 4: Utility system within the homes

4.3 Water system assessment

Water is life and is needed to meet daily needs such as washing, cooking, cleaning, drinking etc. Nsutem as a community do not have a common water source system where each household gets water to meet daily needs. Most of the water sources are boreholes provided by Community and Water and Sanitation Agency in Ghana. These boreholes are provided at vantage points where each household members goes to fetch on daily basis. Some also have standing pipes which have been

extended to the houses to serve as water sources. Some also make use of wells in their homes.

Table 3: Main Water System at Home

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Well	26	26.0	26.0	26.0
Standing Pipe	51	51.0	51.0	77.0
Borehole System	14	14.0	14.0	91.0
Rain Water	8	8.0	8.0	99.0
Well anad Standing Pipe	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the 100 sample space, 26 respondents representing 26% have wells in their homes as depicted in **Table 3**. It's these wells which are used to serve all kinds of water needs in the homes. These wells have health issues as some are dug near to toilet facilities. There is the possibility there will be seepage from the toilet facilities into the wells posing threats to human health. 51 people representing 51 percent have standing pipes in the homes to meet daily needs. They indicated that, the standing pipes within the homes are helping as it saves time if not, inhabitants would have spent some hours assessing water from outside the home. 8 respondents as seen in **Fig 5** said, they depend on rain water for their daily water needs in the homes. Once it gets to the dry season, they depend on the borehole

built by Community Water and Sanitation Agency within the community.

Fig 5: Main water system used in the homes

4.4 Sanitation System practiced in homes

Sanitation system within the homes is of utmost importance to the wellbeing of man as one needs to get rid of metabolic waste from his or her system on daily basis. As we eat on daily basis, waste are generated within the body which one need to get rid of always. Access to sanitation system within the homes and in Nsutem community is limited and inadequate as certain areas within the community especially the study areas do not have

such facility to support daily lives. The research sorted to access the various sanitation facilities used within the homes in order to meet the sustainable development goal six in Nsutem community. 44 respondents representing 44% indicated that they have water closed (pour – flash toilets) in the homes to support the disposal of human waste within their homes as shown in **Table 4**. Respondents indicated that making use of the water closet in the homes is beneficial and hygienic but has an associated disadvantage. The disadvantage is that, it increases water tariffs as a lot of water is used in homes with large numbers.

Table 4: Sanitation system Practiced at Home

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Water Closet (Pour - flash toilets)	44	44.0	44.0	44.0
Pit Latrines	31	31.0	31.0	75.0
Composting Toilets	22	22.0	22.0	97.0
Aqua privies	1	1.0	1.0	98.0
Other	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

31 respondents indicating 31% makes use of pit latrines in their homes as way of meeting sanitation demands as seen in **Fig 6**. Some of the pit latrines are constructed close to wells and that is not hygienic as it may results in seepage from latrines into

wells during rainfalls. The use of composting toilets constituted 22% of the respondents during the investigations in Nsutem community. Aqua privies is by 1 respondents representing 1% and others are 2 representing 2% of the sample space. The others represent people who makes use of bushes and garden to ease themselves or get rid of human waste in other to meet sanitation needs within the homes and in Nsutem community in the Eastern Region of Ghana.

Fig 6: Type of Sanitation systems practiced in the homes

The income draining utility in the home was also analyzed to access the most utility which inhabitants within the study area

are spending much money on. As depicted in Table 5., the most income draining utility is on electricity. 98 respondents representing 98% indicated that, they spend much on electricity as compared to other utilities such as on water. This is because they need light for all kinds of activities such as entertainment, for their stores, for ironing other power usage activities in the homes. 2 respondents representing 2% indicated that, they spend their money on buying water from boreholes to meet water demands in the homes. This can be seen in Fig.

Table 5: Most income draining utility

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Water System	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
Electricity System	98	98.0	98.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Fig. 7: Income draining utility in the homes

4.5 Open defecation and refuse disposal system

After accessing and analyzing the sanitation systems within the homes, open defecation within the study area was also accessed and analyzed. It was to find out whether open defecation was still been practiced within the community. 94 respondents representing 94% said no meaning open defecation was not seen within the area as depicted in Table 6. But 2 people representing 2% said open defecation is still being practiced around their area. Their reason was that, people continue to defecate in their gardens and the back of the houses when bushy as can be seen in Fig 8.

Table 6: Open defecation experience within community

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	6	6.0	6.0	6.0
No	94	94.0	94.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Most people within the community do not have toilet facilities in their homes hence resort to different ways of accessing toilet facilities within the community. This includes visiting other people’s homes to access the facility, going to public toilet facilities or practicing open defecations at the back of the houses in bushes or in gardens. This has been going on over the ages but modernization has decreased the practice drastically within the community. So the research work sorted to see if this practice is out of the system or still being practiced within the community in this modern Ghana in Nsutem community.

Fig 8: Open defecation practice within the study area

Human activities generates tons of waste disposal each day as they go about their daily activities in the homes and in the environment. Nsutem community is no exception as tons of waste are generated on daily basis. The environment and surrounding become tidy and healthy when these waster are managed and disposed carefully. Improper management and disposal of such waste leads to the generation of pathogens which causes diseases and illness to humans. The waste disposal system within the study area was accessed and analyzed to see the waste management practices within the community. 7 respondents representing 7% indicated that, the

waste disposal system of the community is very poor. This is because, they see refuse within the environment all the time making it unhealthy and untidy. This leads to high pathogens generation which can cause diseases and ill health. 42 respondents representing 42% indicated that the waste disposal system is good while 47% said it is very good. This is so because they believe the waste bins provided by waste management organization at vantage points helps households to dispose their refuse very well. This is depicted in **Table 7** and in **Fig. 9**.

Table 7: Nature of refuse disposal system

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Poor	7	7.0	7.0	7.0
Good	42	42.0	42.0	49.0
Very Good	47	47.0	47.0	96.0
Excellent	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

4 respondents representing 4% indicated that the waste disposal practice within their area in the Nsutem community is excellent. This was seen around areas where people live in self – contained owned apartments within the study area. Such areas are very hygienic and tidy with fresh air to breath always. They are areas with new built buildings as compared to the old locations within the study area. There is a refuse management

company which has provided waste disposal bins at vantage points and allows inhabitants to dispose their waste at such vantage points at a fee. This is well practiced in some areas within the study area while others do not dispose them there. Such people burn the waste materials in their gardens or at the back of their houses and this makes such areas untidy and unhealthy.

Fig 9: Waste disposal practices within the study area

5 CONCLUSION

Water and sanitation needs is a requirement needed to be fulfill by each home within Nsutem community in the Eastern

Region of Ghana. Illegal gold mining activities in Nsutem has destroyed all the water bodies such as river Birim which inhabitants within the community were using to meet daily needs. This has resulted to the use of Borehole water to support daily water needs in the community. Research investigations indicated that, people make use of well water, borehole, rainwater or standing pipe water from Community Water and Sanitation Agency to meet daily demands. Upon sampling 100 respondents within the study area, 51% indicated that they make use of standing pipes which has been constructed by community water and Sanitation Agency to access water for the homes in meeting daily water needs. This water is used to meet daily water demands such as cooking, washing, cleaning bathing etc and for flushing toilets in the homes. 44 respondents representing 44% indicated that they have water closed (pour – flush toilets) in the homes to support the disposal of human waste within their homes. Respondents indicated that electricity is the main utility which they spend much of the monthly earnings on as they need light for all kinds of activities both during the day and at night. 94 respondents representing 94% said no, meaning open defecation is not seen within the study area. But 2 people representing 2% said open defecation is still being practiced around their area. Their reason was that, people continue to defecate in their gardens and the back of the houses when bushy.

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REFERENCES

- Allegranzi B., Nejad S. B., Combescure C., et al., 2011, "Burden of endemic health-care-associated infection in developing countries: systematic review and meta-analysis," *The Lancet*, vol. 377, no. 9761, pp. 228–241.
- Bartram J., Lewis K., Lenton R, and Wright A., 2005 "Focusing on improved water and sanitation for health," *The Lancet*, vol. 365, no. 9461, pp. 810–812.
- Cairncross, S., Shordt, K., 2004. It does last! Some findings from a multi-country study of hygiene sustainability. *Waterlines* 22, 4–7, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3362/0262-8104.2004.003>.
- Cameron, L., Olivia, S., Shah, M., 2015. Initial Conditions Matter: Social Capital and Participatory Development.
- Cavill, S., Chambers, R., Vernon, N., 2014. Sustainability and CLTS: Taking Stock, *Front. CLTS Innov. Insights*, 30 pp.=.
- Crocker, J., Bogle, J., 2015. Community-led Total Sanitation in Ghana: Findings from a Situational Assessment [WWW Document], <http://waterinstitute.unc.edu/files/2015/03/situational-assessment-ghana-2015-02.pdf>.
- Crocker, J., Rowe, R., 2015. Community-led Total Sanitation in Ethiopia: Findings from a Situational Assessment, [WWW Document], <http://waterinstitute.unc.edu/files/2015/03/situational-assessment-ethiopia-2015-02.pdf>
<http://waterinstitute.unc.edu/files/2015/03/situational-assessment-ethiopia-201502.pdf>.
- Crocker, J., Abodoo, E., Asamani, D., Domapielle, W., Gyapong, B., Bartram, J., 2016a. Impact evaluation of training natural leaders during a community-led total sanitation intervention: a cluster-randomized field trial in Ghana. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 8867–8875, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b01557>.
- Crocker, J., Geremew, A., Atalie, F., Yetie, M., Bartram, J., 2016b. Teachers and sanitation promotion: an assessment of community-led total sanitation in Ethiopia. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 6517–6525, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b01021>.
- Cronk R., Slaymaker T., and Bartram J., 2015, "Monitoring drinking water, sanitation, and hygiene in non-household settings: priorities for policy and practice," *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, vol. 218, no. 8, pp. 694–703.
- Cronk R., and Bartram J., 2018, "Environmental conditions in health care facilities in low- and middle-income countries: coverage and inequalities," *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, vol. 221, no. 3, pp. 409–422.
- Garn, J.V., Sclar, G.D., Freeman, M.C., Penakalapati, G., Alexander, K.T., Brooks, P., Rehfuess, E.A., Boisson, S., Medlicott, K.O., Clasen, T.F., 2016. The impact of sanitation interventions on latrine coverage and latrine use: a systematic review and meta analysis. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.10.001>.
- Guo A., Kayser G., Bartram J., and Bowling J. M., 2017, "Water, sanitation, and hygiene in rural health-care facilities:

a cross-sectional study in Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, Rwanda, Uganda, and Zambia, "American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, vol. 97, no. 4, pp. 1033–1042.

- Guiteras, R., Levinsohn, J., Mobarak, A.M., 2015. Encouraging sanitation investment in the developing world: a cluster-randomized trial. *Science* 348, 903–906, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa0491>.
- Hoque, B.A., Juncker, T., Sack, R.B., Ali, M., Aziz, K.M.A., 1996. Sustainability of a water, sanitation and hygiene education project in rural Bangladesh: a 5-year follow-up. *Bull. World Health Organ.* 74, 431–437.
- Institute of Development Studies, 2016. The CLTS Approach [WWW Document], <http://www.Community led total sanitation.org/page/clts-approach> (accessed 09.30.16).
- Kar, K., Chambers, R., 2008. Handbook on Community-led Total Sanitation. Plan UK and Institute of Development Studies.
- Pickering, A.J., Djebbari, H., Lopez, C., Coulibaly, M., Alzua, M.L., 2015. Effect of a community-led sanitation intervention on child diarrhoea and child growth in rural Mali: a cluster-randomised controlled trial. *Lancet Glob. Health* 3, e701–e711, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(15\)00144-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(15)00144-8).
- UN General Assembly, 2015. Draft Outcome Document of the United Nations Summit for the Adoption of the Post-2015 Development Agenda., <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199560103.003.0005>
- Waddington, H., Snilstveit, B., White, H., Fewtrell, L., 2009. Water Sanitation and Hygiene Interventions to Combat Childhood Diarrhoea in Developing Countries.
- WHO/UNICEF, 2015. Progress on Sanitation and Drinking Water: 2015 Update and MDG Assessment. Geneva, Switzerland.
- WHO, WHO/UNICEF Report: Water, Sanitation and Hygiene in Health Care Facilities: Status in Low- and Middle-Income Countries and Way Forward Question and Answer, WHO, 2015, Geneva, Switzerland, http://who.int/water_sanitation_health/publications/qa-wash-hcf.pdf.
- WHO/UNICEF, Water, Sanitation and Hygiene in Health Care Facilities: Status in Low- and Middle-Income Countries and Way Forward, WHO, 2015, Geneva, Switzerland.

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